

HYDROLYSIS OF LEAD^{II} AND ITS EFFECT ON THE SOLUBILITY OF LEAD IODATE

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Sn^{II} and Pb^{II} are found to be more hydrolysed in aqueous solution than some other divalent ions of comparatively smaller radii. The hydrolysis in some cases depends on the capacity of the cation to form covalent bond, besides on charge and radius. The hydrolysis of divalent lead ion might be represented by,

and

taking place in two steps. The extent of hydrolysis depends on the activity of water, and therefore expected to be appreciable in very dilute solution of lead salts. In a saturated aqueous solution of lead iodate, the hydrolysis is found to be appreciable and $4S^3$ (where S is the solubility of lead iodate in g. mole per litre at a given ionic strength at 35°) does not represent the solubility product of lead iodate. $4S^3$ is equal to $K_1 \times [\text{H}^+] + K_2 \times k$ (where K_1 is a constant, k is the equilibrium constant of the reaction (1) and $[\text{H}^+]$ is the molar concentration of hydrogen ion). Hence $4S^3$ at lower p_H is hydrogen-dependent, whereas at higher p_H , the factor $K_2 \times [\text{H}^+]$ being smaller compared to $K_2 \cdot k$, it is independent of p_H . The mean value of k is 0.121.

The Pb²⁺ ion with ionic radius of 1.21 Å, which is greater than those of Ca²⁺ (0.99 Å) and Sr²⁺ (1.13 Å), is known to hydrolyse in aqueous solution to an appreciable extent, giving rise to basic salts, many of which have been isolated in the free state. This shows that the charge/radius ratio is not the only factor that can account for the electrical character or the electronegativity of the element or its ions. The electronic structure and the position of the element in the Periodic Table are primarily responsible for electron affinity and electronegativity of the elements. It is only in the case of similar elements of the same vertical group in the Periodic Table that charge/radius ratio determines their relative electrochemical behaviour. Many of the inorganic lead compounds therefore show covalent character, particularly the halides and the oxides. Standing just above hydrogen in the electropotential series of elements, lead shows rather a weak electropositive character and behaves as an amphoteric element. Such elements, when occur as positive ion, tend to attract electrons from other groups or molecules, giving rise to the formation of complexes. Pb²⁺ in aqueous solution therefore tends to attract and hold around itself one or more water molecules, and thereby suffer hydrolysis.

The hydrolysis of Pb²⁺ can be assumed to be taking place in two steps, as represented below.

The hydrolysis, being dependent on the activity of water, is expected to be high in very dilute solutions of lead salts. In a saturated solution of sparingly soluble salt therefore, the hydrolysis would be appreciable. The hydrolysis of lead sulphate solution

has been observed previously (Pleissner, *Arb. Kaiser. Ges. Amt.*, 1907, 26, 419; Sehual, *Compt. rend.*, 1909, 148, 1394). Recently, hydrolysis of mercurous chloride in aqueous solution has been reported (Dry and Gledhill, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1955, 51, 1119).

If lead ion hydrolyses, as suggested above, in a saturated aqueous solution of lead iodate, the concentration of lead ion would be p_H -dependent, besides depending on the concentration of iodate ion. The solubility would change with p_H . To verify this the solubility of lead iodate in perchloric acid of different concentrations was determined. It was, however, assumed that perchlorate and iodate ions did not form complex with lead.

EXPERIMENTAL

Lead iodate was prepared after La Mer and Goldman (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 52, 2791). Chemicals used were of G. R. quality. Perchloric acid and sodium perchlorate used were prepared from 70% perchloric acid. The solubilities were measured at $35^\circ \pm 0.2^\circ$. The same sample of lead iodate was used throughout the investigation. The solubilities of lead iodate in (1) sodium perchlorate solution of different concentrations (0.3–0.02 M), (2) perchloric acid solution of the same concentration as sodium perchlorate, (3) mixture of sodium perchlorate and perchloric acid of the same ionic strength and (4) mixture of perchloric acid and potassium iodate were determined. The results are shown in Tables IA, IB, IC and ID respectively, where S represents the solubility in g. moles of lead iodate per litre. The concentrations in g. moles per litre are expressed by square brackets.

TABLE IA

In NaClO_4 .

$[\text{NaClO}_4]$	$S \times 10^5$
0.30	9.860
0.25	9.520
0.20	9.175
0.18	9.005
0.16	8.660
0.14	8.485
0.12	8.230
0.10	8.060
0.08	7.720
0.06	7.205
0.04	6.860
0.02	6.515
0.00	5.085

TABLE IB

In HClO_4 .

$[\text{HClO}_4]$	$S \times 10^5$
0.30	15.17
0.25	13.95
0.20	12.73
0.18	12.02
0.16	11.50
0.14	10.98
0.12	10.37
0.10	9.590
0.08	8.980
0.06	8.865
0.04	7.495
0.02	6.530
0.00	5.085

TABLE IC

In mixture of NaClO_4 and HClO_4 .

$[\text{HClO}_4]$	$[\text{NaClO}_4]$	$S \times 10^5$
0.30	0.00	15.17
0.25	0.05	14.23
0.20	0.10	13.43
0.18	0.12	12.90
0.16	0.14	12.64
0.14	0.15	12.21
0.12	0.18	11.86
0.10	0.20	11.51
0.08	0.22	11.16
0.06	0.24	10.72
0.04	0.26	10.37
0.02	0.28	9.86

TABLE II

Solubility in mixture of HClO_4 and KIO_3 .

$[\text{HClO}_4]$	$[\text{KIO}_3] \times 10^5$	$S \times 10^5$	$S \times [\text{IO}_3^-]^2 \times 10^{12}$
0.20	0.00	12.73	8.250
0.20	6.667	10.87	8.835
0.20	8.000	10.47	8.974
0.20	9.333	10.14	8.888
0.20	10.67	9.555	8.476
0.20	12.00	9.315	8.735
0.20	13.33	8.910	8.648
0.20	16.63	8.115	8.764

TABLE II

Ionic strength = 0.30

$[\text{H}^+]$	$[\text{PbOH}^+] \times 10^5$	$[\text{Pb}^{2+}] \times 10^5$	k_1
0.30	4.157	11.010	0.113
0.25	4.316	9.914	0.109
0.20	4.854	8.585	0.113
0.18	5.252	7.648	0.124
0.16	5.469	7.171	0.122
0.14	5.862	6.348	0.129
0.12	6.213	5.647	0.132
0.10	6.595	4.915	0.134
0.08	7.020	4.140	0.136
0.06	7.608	3.112	0.146
0.04	8.127	2.243	0.145

TABLE III

Ionic strength.	$[\text{H}^+]$	$[\text{PbOH}^+] \times 10^5$	$[\text{Pb}^{2+}] \times 10^5$	k_1
0.30	0.30	4.157	11.010	0.113
0.25	0.25	4.432	9.518	0.116
0.20	0.20	4.766	7.964	0.120
0.18	0.18	4.903	7.297	0.121
0.16	0.16	4.910	6.590	0.119
0.14	0.14	5.093	5.887	0.121
0.12	0.12	5.183	5.187	0.120
0.10	0.10	5.693	3.879	0.146
0.08	0.08	5.705	3.274	0.139

TABLE IV

Ionic strength = 0.20. $[\text{H}^+] = 0.20$.

$[\text{PbOH}^+] \times 10^5$	$[\text{Pb}^{2+}] \times 10^5$	k_1
4.766	7.964	0.120
3.827	7.043	0.109
3.691	6.769	0.109
3.525	6.515	0.107
3.482	6.073	0.115
3.294	6.021	0.109
3.184	5.726	0.111
2.861	5.254	0.109

DISCUSSION

The increase in the solubility of lead iodate with increasing concentration of sodium perchlorate is most probably due to the increasing ionic strength since an increase in the solubility of a similar order with the increasing ionic strength is observed in the solubility of barium iodate in potassium chloride, nitrate, chlorate and perchlorate solutions (Seidell, "Solubilities of Inorganic and Metal Organic Compounds", 3rd. Ed., 1940, Vol. I, p. 168). The solubility in perchloric acid is, however, higher than that in sodium perchlorate of the same ionic strength. This might be due to some reaction involving hydrogen ion. This is further confirmed by the solubilities in mixtures of sodium perchlorate and perchloric acid of constant ionic strength (the concentration of lead iodate being small, its contribution to the ionic strength is neglected). The solubility increases with increasing concentration of hydrogen ion. The activity coefficients are taken to be constant at constant ionic strength. It is assumed that the solubility product ($4S^3$) is directly proportional to the n th power of the concentration of H^+ ion. Hence,

$$4S^3 = K \times [\text{H}^+]^n \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

Taking logarithm to the base 10,

$$\log 4 + 3 \log S = \log K + n \log [H^+] \quad \dots \quad (3-1)$$

or
$$3 \log S = \log K_1 + n \log [H^+] \quad \dots \quad (3-2)$$

$$3pS = p K_1 + n p_n \quad \dots \quad (3-3)$$

The solubilities in the mixture of sodium perchlorate and perchloric acid of constant ionic strength were used. The concentration of hydrogen ion was taken to be equal to the concentration of perchloric acid. In Fig. 1, $3pS$ is plotted against p_n . The plot is a smooth curve with changing slope. The slope at lower p_n is 1, whereas at higher p_n , it approaches zero. $4S^3$ is proportional to the concentration of hydrogen ion at lower p_n , but is independent of it at higher p_n . Strictly speaking, $4S^3$ does not represent the solubility product of lead iodate.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

The p_n and ionic strength of the saturated solution of lead iodate in 0.2M-HClO₄ containing a small amount of KIO₃ can be taken as constant. The solubility decreases with increasing concentration of iodate ion. It is assumed that the solubility of lead iodate is inversely proportional to the m th power of the concentration of iodate ion at constant H⁺-ion concentration. Hence,

$$S \times [IO_3^-]^m = K_2 \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

Taking logarithm to the base 10

$$\log S = \log K_2 - m \log [IO_3^-] \quad \dots \quad (4-1)$$

In Fig. 2 $\log S$ is plotted against $-\log [IO_3^-]$; the plot is a straight line with the slope equal to 2. At constant p_n therefore S , *i.e.* total lead in the solution, is inversely proportional to the square of the concentration of iodate ion. (The value of $S \times [IO_3^-]^2$ is given in the last column of Table Id and is fairly constant).

$$S \times [IO_3^-]^2 = K_3 \quad \dots \quad (4-2)$$

If no potassium iodate be added, $[IO_3^-] = 2S$, and

$$4S^3 = K_3 \quad \dots \quad (4-3)$$

The above equation (4-3) holds good at constant p_n . The relationship between total lead and iodate ion confirms the assumption that no iodate complex of lead is formed at the concentration of iodate ion of the order of the solubility of lead iodate.

The changes in the solubility and in the value of $4S^3$ with change in p_H are most probably due to hydrolysis of lead ion, as represented by equations (1) and (2). The equilibrium constants at a given ionic strength may be represented by equation (1-1) and (2-1) respectively.

$$\frac{[\text{Pb OH}^+] \times [\text{H}^+]}{[\text{Pb}^{2+}]} = k_1 \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (1-1)$$

$$\frac{[\text{Pb(OH)}_2] \times [\text{H}^+]}{[\text{PbOH}^+]} = k_2 \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (2-1)$$

The total lead in the solution [Pb] (is equal to S) is given by

$$[\text{Pb}] = [\text{Pb}^{2+}] + [\text{PbOH}^+] + [\text{Pb(OH)}_2] \quad \dots \quad (7)$$

$$= [\text{Pb}^{2+}] \left(1 + \frac{k_1}{[\text{H}^+]} + \frac{k_1 \times k_2}{[\text{H}^+]^2} \right) \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (7-1)$$

If the second hydrolysis is assumed to have taken place to a small extent, compared to first, the concentration of Pb(OH)_2 would be small and may be neglected. Hence,

$$[\text{Pb}] = [\text{Pb}^{2+}] \times \left(1 + \frac{k_1}{[\text{H}^+]} \right) \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (7-2)$$

or
$$S = [\text{Pb}^{2+}] \left(1 + \frac{k_1}{[\text{H}^+]} \right) \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (7-3)$$

The above equation indicates that (i) when total lead, *i. e.* iodate ion, is constant $[\text{Pb}^{2+}]$ varies with the concentration of hydrogen ion, and (ii) when the concentration of hydrogen ion is constant, $[\text{Pb}^{2+}]$ is directly proportional to the total lead. It has been shown before that at constant p_H , S , *i. e.* total lead, is inversely proportional to the square of the concentration of iodate ion; the same relationship is therefore true of lead ion. It follows therefore that

$$\frac{[\text{Pb}^{2+}] \times [\text{IO}_3^-]^2}{[\text{H}^+]} = K_s \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (8)$$

where K_s is a constant.

$4S^3$ is actually the product of the concentration of total lead and the square of the concentration of iodate ion.

$$4S^3 = [\text{Pb}] \times [\text{IO}_3^-]^2 \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (9)$$

$$= [\text{Pb}^{2+}] \times \left(1 + \frac{k_1}{[\text{H}^+]} \right) \times [\text{IO}_3^-]^2 \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (9-1)$$

$$= K_s \times [\text{H}^+] \times \left(1 + \frac{k_1}{[\text{H}^+]} \right) \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (9-2)$$

or
$$4S^3 = K_s \times [\text{H}^+] + K_s \times k_1 \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (9-3)$$

$4S^3$ is the sum of a p_H -dependent and a constant term and it is directly proportional to the concentration of H^+ .

When p_H is high and k_1 is greater than $[\text{H}^+]$, the p_H -dependent term, $K_s \times [\text{H}^+]$ becomes small and $4S^3$ is given by $K_s \times k_1$. The equation (9-3) satisfactorily explains the experimental curve in Fig. 1 and confirms the assumption that the second hydrolysis of lead ion has taken place to a very small extent.

The μ -dependent term would be small and therefore negligible in the neutral solution. The term $K_s k_1$, which is constant, is equal to $4S_0^3$, where S_0 is the solubility of lead iodate in sodium perchlorate solution of the same ionic strength. The equation (9-3) therefore reduces to

$$4S^3 = K_s' [H^+] + 4S_0^3 \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (10)$$

or $4S^3 - 4S_0^3 = K_s [H^+] \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (10-1)$

or $4S^3 - 4S_0^3 = [Pb^{2+}] \times [IO_3^-]^2 \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (10-2)$
 $[IO_3^-]$ being equal to $2S$,

$$\frac{4S^3 - 4S_0^3}{4S^2} = [Pb^{2+}] \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (10-3)$$

or $S - (S_0^3/S^2) = [Pb^{2+}] \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (10-4)$

$[Pb^{2+}] + [PbOH^+] = S$, hence,

$$S_0^3/S^2 = [PbOH^+] \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (10-5)$$

The concentration of $PbOH^+$ is calculated by equation (10-5). The concentration of lead ion is obtained by subtracting $[PbOH^+]$ from S , the solubility of lead iodate in perchloric acid or mixture of perchloric acid and sodium perchlorate of a given ionic strength. The concentration of hydrogen ion is taken to be equal to the concentration of perchloric acid. k_1 , calculated by equation (1-1), is given below. The results obtained from (i) the solubility in $0.3M$ - $NaClO_4$ (S_0) and those in $NaClO_4$ and $HClO_4$ of the same ionic strength (S), (ii) the solubility in $NaClO_4$ (S_0) and those in $HClO_4$ of the same concentration (S) and that in $0.2M$ - $NaClO_4$ (S_0) and those in $0.2M$ - $HClO_4$ containing very small amount of KIO_3 (S) are recorded in Tables I-IV respectively. k_1 is fairly constant and the mean value is 0.121. k_1 can also be obtained graphically. If $4S^3$ is plotted against $[H^+]$, the equation (9-3) indicates that a straight line would be obtained, the slope of which would give the value of K_s and the intercept, that of $K_s \times k_1$. The solubilities in the mixtures of sodium perchlorate and perchloric acid (constant ionic strength) were used. Most of the points lie very close to a straight line. The slope is 3.0×10^{-11} and the intercept is 3.3×10^{-12} . k_1 is therefore 0.11. This is in agreement with the calculated value.

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